

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See informed consent sheet

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized transcript of recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	16/07/2021
Name of the interviewer	ALFONSO EGE A DE HARO
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	MANUEL PATO
Affiliation of the expert	REGIONAL FEDERATION OF MUNICIPALITIES OF MURCIA
Position/Job description	SECRETARY-GENERAL
Gender	MALE
Years of experience	MORE THAN 10 YEARS
Area of expertise	MANAGEMENT
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL AND URBAN

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Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	<p>In your opinion, are there differences between rural and urban local entities in relation to their interests or main concerns? If so, what are the main differences between rural and urban governments?</p>
	<p>Rurality is located in a very specific area (municipalities located in the northwestern) and in those municipalities of a "mixed" character that have the characteristics of urban centers but with rural areas (<i>pedanías</i>). The interests are specific and are linked to factors related to agricultural production or the occurrence of phenomena such as depopulation. It is evident in this case how depopulation is not a common phenomenon throughout the regions.</p>
2	<p><i>Do these differences have any consequences on the organization of the association? What mechanisms are in place to ensure equal representation between rural and urban municipalities?</i></p>
	<p>Representation is determined by population, but there are corrective mechanisms that "guarantee" the representation of the municipalities regardless of their population. The current scheme foresees a minimum of 4 representatives for each municipality and a cap in the linear increase in the number of representatives from 100,000 inhabitants upwards. In this way, the diversity in the number of representatives between rural and urban municipalities is contained, ranging from 4 to 12 representatives.</p>
3	<p>Do all the local authorities of the Autonomous Community participate in the association?</p>
	<p>All the municipalities do participate (45); their participation is essential given that being a one-province Autonomous Community reduces the resources allocated to the province-level and therefore the local level of government; in one-province Autonomous Communities the resources allocated to one of the local governments –provinces- is managed by the regional government). This situation regarding the constraints in financial resources is permanently criticized by the local entities. In addition, the lack of resources is represented by the fact that membership quotas have been raised recently.</p>

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OPERATION OF THE ASSOCIATION

4	What is the main source of the association's financial resources? What is the importance of the regional and general levels of government in terms of financing?
	The resources come from the contributions of the municipalities as well as from the regional funds, although a constant demand by local authorities is the development of a comprehensive regulatory framework regarding economic resources and finance mechanisms at the local level. This aspect is a priority for local governments, together with the regulatory development of a so-called "second decentralization process" from the regions to the municipalities (a project promoted by the FEMP).
5	Is there a permanent body for the management and representation of local authorities, how are its members elected, are there quotas or guarantees for the representation of less populated local authorities?
	The most important permanent body is the General Secretariat, which organizes the various sectoral committees where, more than a territorial representation, a balance is met between the different ideological options due to the composition of sectoral committees. To this regard, the committees are chaired by a representative of the major political parties alternating presidency and vice-presidency positions.
6	What are the main mechanisms used by the association to identify priority issues?
	The agenda is mostly determined by the guidelines identified by the presidency of the federation. These guidelines are approved in the assembly and sets the agenda for a four-years period. The General Secretariat distributes the task of drawing up the guidelines among the different sectoral commissions that have been set up. These characteristics in the formation of the agenda show a higher level of independence than that identified in other cases such as in Navarra or Andalusia where the agenda was largely dependent on the main role of the Federation in analyzing the regulation proposals submitted to the federation to inform about the compliance with the local autonomy principle.
	<i>Are working groups created on specific issues -population, aging, social services, digital agenda-?</i>

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	There are sectoral commissions that assume the different sectoral thematic lines (agriculture, water and environment; culture, education, youth and sports; employment, tourism and local development; Europe and external relations; financing, competencies and local finances, among others). These commissions largely reproduce the organizational structure of the regional government.
8	What role does party affiliation play in the decision-making processes within the association?
	The alignment is relevant as can be seen from the composition of the commissions where the chairman and vice-chairman are from the main political parties.
9	Which decision rule is most frequently used within the association: majority vote, unanimity, consensus?
	Consensus.
10	Are there mechanisms to ensure compliance with the agreements?
	As a consequence of the importance of consensus, agreements are "self-executing" in nature.

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

RELATIONS WITH OTHER LEVELS OF GOVERNMENT

11	Which level of government - regional, general government - is the one with which you have the most direct relationship?
	Regional and central levels.
12	What type of relationship is the priority: technical, financial, etc.?
	The main type of relationship is of technical nature. The main area in which interaction between the different levels of government takes place is the monitoring of regional legislative projects in order to preserve local autonomy.
13	Is there any permanent coordination body with the Autonomous Administration? If so, what is its purpose? analysis of legislative projects? follow-up of program execution?
	Reference to previous question.
14	What role does the FEMP play in relation to the association? technical assistance? financial? other?

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	<p>The FEMP is the main counterpart with the central government (due to its participation in the various sectoral commissions in which the central and regional governments participate). The FEMP also plays a relevant role in determining the relationship with international organizations (as opposed, for example, to the case of Andalusia, where the regional federation reported the direct relationship with the regional government).</p> <p>Influence on the FEMP is also influenced by personal relationships or the presence of members of the regional federation in the FEMP.</p>
15	Are there relations with other organizations? Universities? Business associations? Trade unions?
	There is a framework agreement with different actors with respect to which bilateral relations are developed (universities, labor unions, business associations, among others). The agreements include a follow-up commission that sets the objectives for the following year (this is the case, for example, of the project for the transformation into cooperatives of the companies that are in insolvency proceedings).
16	How do you guarantee the protection of local autonomy in relation to the acts of other public administrations?
	Reference to question 12.
17	What type of relationship exists with the European and international level in general? Is this relationship coordinated directly or through the FEMP, the State General Administration?
	The relationship is through the FEMP.

Part C: Additional Country-Specific Questions

CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROGRAMS

18	What are the main organizational challenges facing the association?
	The main objective is to develop the regulatory framework for the local government (financial aspects, inter-administrative cooperation and local entities partnerships – <i>mancomunidades</i> -, among other aspects). In addition, a main concern for the Federation is to justify its instrumental in promoting the interests of local entities. Finally, the modernization (i.e. digitalization) of the Administration is a pressing issue.

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19	What are the main public policy challenges - social services, depopulation, etc. - faced by the association?
	Reference to previous question
20	What measures are being promoted by the association with a view to achieving a population balance and combating depopulation? Are there differences between local authorities with respect to the measures to be adopted in matters such as depopulation?
	This is a recent issue and it is expected that the regional government will take some action although the limited impact of the depopulation process in the region reduce the concerns and the proposals by the government in this area.
21	What measures are being taken by the association in order to be eligible for and participate in the European funds for recovery and resilience?
	The main problem is that the projects to be financed with those funds usually are better meet in areas area larger than the municipality. This circumstance highlights the need to develop the regional legal framework in matters such as associations of municipalities (<i>mancomunidades</i>).

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